

Tatiana V. SOLOD

*Southern Federal University (Rostov-on-Don, Russia)
PhD in Economics, Associate Professor; e-mail: tsolod@sfedu.ru
ORCID: 0000-0002-0244-5439*

CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE REVISION OF STRATEGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURIST TERRITORIES AS A PREREQUISITE FOR THEIR ADAPTATION TO NEW REALITIES

Abstract. *Recently, tourism has been undergoing significant changes due to both global challenges and internal changes. The growth of competition, changes in technological patterns and consumer preferences, negative political factors, and increased attention to environmental issues require in-depth analysis and revision of tourism development strategies. Reviewing and adapting existing strategies to new realities has become a prerequisite for the successful functioning of tourist areas. The material studied in the course of the research allowed the author to assert that this aspect has been little investigated and requires elaboration. The article presents the author's view on the approach to the revision of the strategies of tourist territories. Namely, the idea has been formed that the revision of strategies should be accompanied by the identification of the stage of the life cycle of the tourism industry of the studied territory, the cyclical development and seasonality of the tourist territory itself. The opinion is given that the life cycle of the tourism industry can no longer be tied to only one indicator of the assessment – the tourist flow, the recommended basic indicators are considered. The life cycle of the tourism industry is considered with the presentation of basic characteristics for its stages, taking into account modern features, the process of revising strategies for the development of the tourist territory is given, basic and functional strategies are grouped. Attention is paid to the issue of linking the strategy revision procedure to specific situations. The conclusions obtained in the course of the study can significantly expand the conceptual foundations of the process of reviewing the strategies for the development of tourist territories.*

Keywords: *basic strategies, functional strategies, cyclicity, life cycle, seasonality, tourist area, assessment indicators*

Citation: Solod, T. V. (2024). Conceptual foundations for the revision of strategies for the development of tourist territories as a prerequisite for their adaptation to new realities. *Servis v Rossii i za rubezhom [Services in Russia and Abroad]*, 18(5), 163–175. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14955720.

Article History

Received 22 October 2024
Accepted 20 December 2024

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest
was reported by the author(s).

© 2024 the Author(s)

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0).

To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

СОЛОД Татьяна Валерьевна

Южный федеральный университет (Ростов-на-Дону, РФ)
кандидат экономических наук, доцент; e-mail: tsolod@sfedu.ru

КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ПЕРЕСМОТРА СТРАТЕГИЙ РАЗВИТИЯ ТУРИСТСКИХ ТЕРРИТОРИЙ КАК ОБЯЗАТЕЛЬНОЕ УСЛОВИЕ ИХ АДАПТАЦИИ К НОВЫМ РЕАЛИЯМ

В последнее время туризм переживает значительные изменения, обусловленные как глобальными вызовами, так и внутренними изменениями. Рост конкуренции, смена технологических укладов, изменения в предпочтениях потребителей, политические факторы негативного характера, усиление внимания экологическим вопросам требуют от стратегий развития туристских территорий глубокого анализа и пересмотра. Пересмотреть и адаптировать существующие стратегии к новым реалиям стало обязательным условием успешного функционирования туристских территорий. Изученный в ходе исследования материал позволил автору утверждать, что данный аспект мало изучен и требует проработки. В статье представлен авторский взгляд на подход к пересмотру стратегий туристских территорий. А именно, сформировано представление о том, что пересмотр стратегий должен сопровождаться выявлением этапа жизненного цикла туристской отрасли изучаемой территории, цикличности развития и сезонности самой туристской территории. Приведено мнение о том, что жизненный цикл туристской отрасли больше не может быть привязан только к одному показателю оценки – туристскому потоку, отдельно рассмотрены рекомендуемые базовые показатели. Отдельно рассмотрен жизненный цикл туристской отрасли с приведением базовых характеристик для его этапов с учётом современных особенностей, дан процесс пересмотра стратегий развития туристской территории, сгруппированы базовые и функциональные стратегии. Уделено внимание вопросу привязки процедуры пересмотра стратегий к конкретным ситуациям. Полученные в ходе исследования выводы могут значительным образом расширить концептуальные основы процесса пересмотра стратегий развития туристских территорий.

Ключевые слова: базовые стратегии, функциональные стратегии, цикличность, жизненный цикл, сезонность, туристская территория, показатели оценки

Для цитирования: Солод Т.В. Концептуальные основы пересмотра стратегий развития туристских территорий как обязательное условие их адаптации к новым реалиям // Сервис в России и за рубежом. 2024. Т.18. №5. С. 163–175. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14955720.

Дата поступления в редакцию: 22 октября 2024 г.

Дата утверждения в печать: 20 декабря 2024 г.

Introduction

In the context of the modern development of the national economy, the tourism sector faces many challenges, which creates the need for the formation of adaptive mechanisms that would allow it to quickly respond to changes in the external and internal environment. The revision of strategies for the development of tourist areas is becoming an important tool for creating flexible and sustainable models that can meet the requirements of the modern market and ensure the quality of life of the local population. The revision of strategies is important to take into account the high dynamics of changes in consumer preferences, namely, to transform standard approaches to the organization of the service provision process.

The article does not address the issues of developing strategies, but the expediency of their revision, which will make the process of strategic management of tourist territories more flexible and adaptive. If an understanding of the need for strategic planning and management of the tourist territory in the country has been formed, then an understanding of the need for a systematic review of the strategy portfolio based on changes has not yet been fully formed. As a result, the lack of timely revision of strategies leads to the fact that most tourism development programs in Russia do not achieve the set results.

The purpose of the study is to consider some aspects of the conceptual foundations of strategic planning in the management of the development of tourist territories, in the context of a special direction – the revision of strategies based on the theory of the life cycle for the tourism industry, cyclical development and seasonality for the territory.

Within the framework of the conducted research, the reliance is made on general scientific (systematic, generalization, synthesis, analysis, comparison, categorization) and special (statistical, logical-historical) methods that allow to reveal the studied problems. Also, data from the official websites of ministries and departments, Rosstat, and scientific publications on the studied issues were used as initial information.

Theory

The issues of strategic management of the tourist territory are not new, but the high dynamism of the development of economic systems, the presence of negative impact factors contribute to their relevance. The study and critical evaluation of scientific works by domestic and foreign authors allowed us to say that the management of strategies of a tourist territory is most often considered in relation to the life cycle of the tourism industry, the cyclicity and seasonality of the tourist territory [22].

For example, S. Gore and N. Borde in their work indicate that in order to manage the development strategy of the tourism industry, it is advisable to conduct research on the life cycle of a tourist territory. At the same time, they indicate a lack of research within this aspect [15]. K. Andriotis suggested that determining the stage of the life cycle at which a tourist area is located is important, since different stages require different strategies [8]. B. Todorovic noted that the analysis of individual phases of the life cycle of a tourist area is important for the development of measures to increase tourist demand and the sustainability of the destination [23]. S.M. Maralbaieva, N.V. Nikiforova argue that the strategy of a tourist brand should be based on the identification of the stages of the life cycle of a tourist territory [18]. S. Polyzos, D. Tsiotas, A. Kantlis described the importance of the life cycle of a tourist area in planning its development [20]. M. Kubickova, H. Li in their scientific work, highlighted that the correctness of the formation of a strategy for the development of a tourist territory depends on how accurately the stage of its life cycle is identified [17]. The same conclusions were reached in their research I.P. Albaladejo и M.P. Martínez-García [7].

On the other hand, D. Bojanic in his scientific article, back in 2005, considered the probability of dependence between the cycle of development of a tourist territory and the life cycle of the tourism industry [10]. A.Y. Alexandrova and V.E. Dombrovskaya in their article address the issue of the expediency of taking into account cyclicity in

planning the development of the tourism sector, with the fixation of evaluation indicators [1]. E. Kalygina proves the existence of a direct connection between the stage of the life cycle of a tourist territory and the life cycle of tourism industry enterprises [3]. The scientific literature has developed a fairly holistic system of approaches to the cyclostatics of economic systems, the most popular are Kondratiev long waves, Kuznetsov cycles, Kitchin, Juglar, etc. But, there is no universally recognized approach applicable to tourist areas. Although it is worth noting that back in 1982, Y.A. Vedenin in his monograph «Dynamics of territorial recreational systems» considered the recreational system as a set of cycles of actions.

Separately, we can single out a group of researchers who consider the management of strategies for the development of a tourist area in relation to seasonality, for example, G. Galloway [14], R. Butler [11], C.A. Barbu, A. Popa [9], R. Canas [13], P. Rizal, R. Asokan [21], etc.

In our opinion, the emphasis on only one of the categories – the life cycle, cyclicity or seasonality does not seem relevant in modern realities. Tourism has acquired the features of a complex system, therefore, all three categories in the conceptual framework of strategic management of the tourist territory should be analyzed and taken into account, both at the stage of forming a portfolio of strategies and its subsequent revisions.

The results of the study

The study showed that the management and revision of strategies should be based on the definition of the stage of the life cycle of the tourism industry in each individual territory, the allocation of the stage of the development cycle of the territory itself and seasonality. At the same time, a «tourist territory» means a physical space (a municipality or a group of Municipalities), which is characterized by the presence of a common tourist product¹. In other words, it can be a city, a rural district, or even an inner-city territory.

First of all, when selecting a portfolio of strategies, it is worth conducting a study on the

current stage of the life cycle of the tourism industry of the territory. The research is traditionally based on the model of R. Butler, who identified 5 main stages of the life cycle of a tourist territory – exploration, involvement, development, consolidation, stagnation (prolonged stagnation, rejuvenation, decline) [2]. As part of the research was formulated the author's vision of the life cycle of the tourism industry and was given a description of the main characteristics of its stages (Fig. 1).

It should be noted that the revision of the development strategy is advisable at the maturity stage, since at this stage of the life cycle the most favorable time for innovation, technological updates, expansion of the range of tourist services, etc. At this stage, it is easy to return to the stages of development and growth [16].

As the main indicator characterizing the transition from one stage to another, R. Butler has established the percentage of tourists arriving and the ratio of local residents to tourists [12]. In our opinion, this indicator currently cannot be the only determining stage of the life cycle of a tourist territory, since, as noted earlier, now the tourist territory is a more complex system than before. We consider it advisable to make additional accounting – the number of travel companies, accommodation facilities, catering enterprises, the volume of tourist products sold, investments and the level of income from tourism. For example, as shown in Figures 2–8 for the Stavropol Kray.

To form a trend for the period 2024–2026, the extrapolation method was applied in Figures 2–8, adjusted for statistical emissions (2020, the impact of COVID-19). Also, in order to track the indicators discussed above most accurately, it is possible to build dynamics series that take into account indicators over several decades, for example, using the ARIMA program. But the trend and seasonality can be detected on rows of relatively short length, using simple calculations. For example, extrapolation showed a trend towards a decline in the number of catering enterprises in the Stavropol Kray (Fig. 6).

¹ Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 2129-r. On the Strategy for the development of tourism in the Russian Federation for the period up to 2035. 2019. URL: <https://garant.ru/products/ipo/prime/doc/72661648/?ysclid=lzy7otrosz506445256> (Accessed on August 13, 2024).

	Time				
Study	Development	Growth	Maturity	Recession	Decline
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - identification of the current position of the tourist area; - recording of current assessment results; - formation of the foundations and basic directions of the formation of the tourism industry; - determining the feasibility of developing the tourism industry; - a relatively small number of enterprises in the tourism industry; - the absence or minimum amount of investment in tourism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - low growth dynamics of the tourist flow; - a tourism development program has been formed with the participation of local authorities; - increasing the number of representatives of the business environment; - the growing interest of local residents in the industry; - the main tourist flow of their border territories; - indicators of the tourism industry show an unstable trend; - aggressive marketing of the territory, branding. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - intensive advertising campaign; - steady growth of the tourist flow; - increasing the geography of visitors; - construction of new enterprises; - the arrival of investors and large tourist operators; - development of related infrastructure; - formation of local travel brands; - formation of a new regulatory framework; - the cost of tourist services is increasing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tourism is the main source of the territory's budget formation; - the tourist product is standardized; - the indicators continue to grow, but the growth rate is slowly starting to decrease; - there may be an obsolescence of some tourist offer; - territory marketing is not so active; - travel brands are recognized, maybe even on a global level; - reorientation of the entire economic system of the region to tourism; - the price of a vacation is very high, maybe even it is not available to residents. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - clear subsidence in all development indicators; - reduction of financing and investments in the industry; - a decrease in the tourist flow, but it has not yet reached a historical minimum; - obsolescence of the range of services offered, but their prices are not falling; - falling interest in the industry from the public sector; - a drop in sales of a tourist product; - reducing the number of specialized enterprises. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - failure in all indicators of the tourism sector; - lack of interest in visiting tourists; - withdrawal of foreign and large local companies from the market; - reducing the tourist flow to a historical minimum.

Fig. 1 – The life cycle of a tourist area with a description of the main characteristics of its stages [6]

Fig. 2 – Number of travel company at the end of the year, units²

² Federal State Statistics Service. (2023). URL: <https://rosstat.gov.ru/statistics/turizm> (Accessed on August 11, 2024).

Fig. 3 – The number of Russian tourists sent on tours by travel companies within the territory of Russia in 2005-2023, people ²

Fig. 4 – The number of Russian tourists sent on tours by travel companies abroad in 2005–2023, people ²

Fig. 5 – The number of collective accommodation facilities in the Stavropol Krai in 2004–2023, pcs. ²

Fig. 6 – The number of catering establishments in the Stavropol Krai in 2004–2023, pcs. ²

Fig. 7 – The number of tourist packages sold to the population of the Stavropol Krai in 2010–2021, pcs.²

Fig. 8 – Tourist flow to the Stavropol Krai for the period 2010-2023, million people³

In parallel with identifying the stage of the life cycle of the tourism industry, it is worth focusing on identifying the stage of the development cycle of the territory itself. This is important because in world history there are cases when, with the general decline of the tourist territory, the tourism industry was at the stage of recovery (Turkey, Thailand, Singapore, etc.), and vice versa (Japan, Russia, etc.). Each of the situations will require its own set of development strategies.

Do not confuse the cyclical development of the territory and the phenomenon of «seasonality» (Fig. 8). The latter is strictly regular, while the cycle repeats at irregular intervals, and depends on the state of the internal and external environment in the region and the country [1].

The difference between seasonality, the life cycle of the tourism industry and the cyclical development of a tourist destination is also that in order to identify the former, only one indicator is enough – the dynamics of the tourist flow in the context of the year, in order to identify the latter,

it is necessary to study a wider range of indicators – the volume of investments in the tourism industry, income from tourism, the number of enterprises involved in the tourism sector, the number of employees in the field, etc. The analysis of the selected indicators should be over a long period of time, this will allow us to make a more accurate conclusion.

Unfortunately, in the state programs for the development of tourist territories, cyclicity is tied to seasonality. For example, in the Strategy for the Development of Tourism in the Russian Federation for the period up to 2035, seasonality is understood as «a steadily (regularly) recurring cycle of tourist activity characteristic of a tourist territory associated with changes in the conditions of stay of tourists and tourists»⁴.

One of the main directions in the revision of the strategy for the development of the tourist area is to determine the current model of its development. The conducted research made it possible to identify the most common development models (Fig. 9) [4].

³ Otdyhaj na Stavropol'e. Analiticheskaya informaciya [Have a rest in Stavropol. Analytical information]. URL: <https://stavgourism.ru/analiticheskaya-informatsiya/> (Accessed on August 13, 2024).

⁴ Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation No.2129-r. On the Strategy for the development of tourism in the Russian Federation for the period up to 2035. 2019. URL: <https://garant.ru/products/ipo/prime/doc/72661648/?ysclid=lzy7otrosz506445256> (Accessed on August 13, 2024).

Category	Description	Indicators
The life cycle of the tourism industry	1) the period during which the tourism industry goes through certain stages of its development – study, development, growth, maturity, decline and decline; 2) refers to predictable changes in the development of economic systems.	the volume of investments in the tourism industry, income from tourism, the number of enterprises involved in the tourism sector, the volume of tourist flow, the number of employees in the field, etc.
The cyclical nature of the development of the tourist area	1) constantly recurring changes in business activity; 2) more difficult to predict; 3) cyclic oscillation occurs relative to the equilibrium position; 4) occurs regardless of the current stage of development of the territory.	tourist flow by month
Seasonality	1) it is observed systematically throughout the year; 2) it is primarily related to the change of climatic conditions, which are the main factor in choosing this territory as a place of rest.	

Fig. 9 – The concept and indicators of measuring the life cycle of the tourism industry, cyclicity and seasonality of the tourist territory [1]

MODELS OF DEVELOPMENT OF RUSSIAN TERRITORIES

Exporters of Raw materials	Technology Partners	Infrastructure-logistics centers
the model reflects the raw material specifics of economic development	provide technical support to the exporting territories of raw materials	an advantageous EGP allows such regions to occupy a niche of transport hubs
Territories-innovators	National republics	Hubs of power and resources
the territories are hosted and supported by R&D enterprises	with this status, regions can get more powers in some areas	territories with city-millionaire
National Recreation, Tourism and Ecology centers	Depressive territories	
the tourism industry is the basis for the development of the territory	the territory does not have sufficient resources for restoration, and the reason may also be an incorrectly chosen development landmark	

Fig. 10 – Models of the development of Russian territories

Putting into practice the revision of strategies for the development of tourist territories, taking into account the above, would reduce the likelihood of errors and the number of incorrect management decisions. Also, it would minimize costs and save budget money. Figure 10 shows the sequence of actions to revise the portfolio of strategies of the tourist territory, taking into account the

stages of the life cycle, cyclicity and seasonality.

It should be noted that it is advisable to consolidate the revision of the portfolio of strategies for the development of the tourist territory to a certain period of time, to the situation of identifying changes in the dynamics of one of the indicators discussed above, or factors of the internal and external environment (Fig. 11).

Fig. 10 – A sequence of actions to review the strategy portfolio, taking into account the stages of the life cycle of the tourism industry, cyclicity and seasonality of the territory [19]

Conditions for reviewing the portfolio of strategies of the tourist territory		
A certain period of time	Changes in the dynamics of indicators of the development of the tourist area	Changes in the factors of the internal and external environment of the tourist area
It is typical for territories with stable development dynamics. A specific review period is set, for example, once a year.	Constant monitoring of key indicators affecting the tourism potential of the region; first of all, the identification of negative dynamics in order to adjust to possible consequences in time and return to sustainable development. It is necessary for all tourist areas.	The analysis of factors affecting the tourist attractiveness of the region both from the internal environment (the state of infrastructure, personnel, quality, etc.) and the external environment (political situation, innovative trends, social trends, etc.). Assumes the allocation of negative manifestations for timely response.

Fig. 11 – Conditions for reviewing the portfolio of strategies of the tourist territory

Table 1 – Basic strategies for the development of the tourist area

Strategy	Description
1. Growth	The tourist area takes a vector for the development, growth and increase of income from the tourism industry. The implementation of this strategy requires large financial investments, support from representatives of the business environment, the implementation of a large number of industry projects, and the creation of the most favorable conditions for entrepreneurial and investment activities. This is a very complex process that requires careful planning and a lot of attention to innovation, digitalization and personalization of services.
2. Stability	The tourist area is taking a «pause» in the development of the tourism industry. The reason for applying the strategy can be both crisis manifestations in the market and an informed management decision. During the period of application of the strategy, only projects are implemented that are aimed at maintaining and preserving previously achieved results. It requires a deliberate approach and cannot be applied for more than 1 year.
3. U-turn	The tourist area is being rebranded, trying to switch to new types of tourism. There is a gradual abandonment of support for the «classic» types of tourism for the region (most likely due to a change in tourist preferences). This does not mean that the «classic» types of tourism are being eliminated, it's just that over time they receive less and less support from the authorities. Differentiation and diversification strategies are actively used.

The portfolio of development strategies must necessarily be adapted to the natural and acquired advantages of the tourist area. Strategy is a kind of art of planning the development of a tourist area, taking into account long-term goals, trends and patterns [5]. The typology of strategies for the development of a tourist area is an insufficiently researched problem, most authors consider the strategy as a «document», and not as a strategy of behavior. Within the framework of this study, we proceed from the fact that the strategies for the development of tourist territories should be divided into two groups: basic (lay the

main vector of development) and functional (help to adhere to the main vector of development). The development strategies of enterprises with the adaptation of their essence to the strategic management of tourist territories are taken as a basis. The results of the study are presented in the table 1.

It should be noted that within the framework of Figure 12, the most common functional strategies are recorded, the application of which is realistic within the framework of tourist territory management. The classification of functional strategies is debatable, and the study of this issue will be continued in subsequent studies.

The basic strategies are supported by a set of functional ones (Fig. 12).

Conclusion

The conducted research allowed the author to make recommendations on revising the portfolio of strategies for the development of tourist territories based on the analysis of the life cycle of the tourism industry, the development cycle and seasonality of the territory. The recommendation is justified by the fact that, firstly, modern realities are much more dynamic and require more detailed analysis, and secondly, the fact that the tourism industry has long moved into the category of complex systems requires consideration of more of its components. Separately, the author's vision of the stages of the life cycle of the tourism industry is given, with a description of their main characteristics. Also, in modern realities, it is proposed to expand the number of indicators for evaluation.

Within the framework of the article, an understanding has been formed of the need for an operational review of development strategies, either in relation to time, or in relation to external factors and changes in key development indicators, primarily of a negative nature. According to the author, the introduction of the requirement to review development strategies may lead to a more effective search for ways to develop tourist areas by selecting or developing the most appropriate strategies. After all, there is no single rule or universal development strategy. The portfolio

Fig. 12 – Functional strategies for the development of tourist territories

of strategies should be formed depending on the current features of the development of the tourist area. However, the transformation of the conceptual foundations of strategic management of tourist territories, over time, may lead to the formation of adaptive sets of strategies capable of responding to the challenges of the time, which ultimately will contribute to the successful development of the tourism industry in modern realities.

Strategy management should be carried out consciously, with a carefully developed plan for each subsequent stage of the life cycle, this will

help take advantage of a rapidly changing market compared to competitors. As part of the revision process, the formation of a portfolio of strategies for the development of tourist territories should be aimed at preserving the results achieved and reviving traditional segments, starting with sight-seeing and ending with business trips, as well as the active development of new types of tourism and related services. The ultimate goal of strategic management of the tourist area should be the creation of an innovative tourist experience, which will position it as a unique destination.

References

1. Aleksandrova, A. Y., & Dombrovskaya, V. E. (2023). Ciklicheskie processy na rynke turizma: obshchie zakonomernosti i specifika proyavleniya [Cyclical processes in the tourism market: general patterns and specific manifestations]. *Nauchnyj rezul'tat. Tekhnologii biznesa i servisa [Scientific result. Business and service technologies]*, 9(2), 3–22. (In Russ.).
2. Goncharova, N. A., & Kiriyanova, L. G. (2011). Upravlenie zhiznennym ciklom destinacii [Destination Lifecycle Management]. *Izvestiya Tomskogo politekhnicheskogo universiteta. [Proceedings of Tomsk Polytechnic University]*, 6, 52–56. (In Russ.).
3. Kalugina, E. V. (2019). Svyaz' mezhdu zhiznennym ciklom otrasli i zhiznennym ciklom organizacii [Research of the bond between corporate life cycle and industry lifecycle]. In coll.: *Sotsialino-orientirovannoe upravlenie v usloviyakh globalizatsii [Socially oriented management in the conditions of globalization]*. Moscow. (In Russ.).
4. Lapin, A. E., & Vuyko, M. B. (2019). Modeli regional'nogo razvitiya v Rossijskoj Federacii i investicionnye strategii [Regional development models in the Russian Federation and investment strategies]. *Regionologiya [Regionology]*, 27(1), 21–26. (In Russ.).
5. Polyatykina, E. V. (2017). Investicionnaya strategiya i ee rol' v razvitii regiona [Investment strategy and its role in the development of the region]. *Innovacionnaya ekonomika: perspektivy razvitiya i sovershenstvovaniya [Innovative economy: prospects for development and improvement]*, 1, 289–293. (In Russ.).
6. Tugeeva, K. M. (2020). Zpiznennyj cikl razvitiya turistskoj destinacii. Model' R. Batlera [The life cycle of the development of a tourist destination. R. Butler's model]. *Tribuna uchenogo [Tribune of the Scientist]*, 5, 1–6. (In Russ.).
7. Albaladejo, I. P., & Martínez-García, M. P. (2019). Congestion affecting the dynamic of tourism demand: Evidence from the most popular destinations in Spain. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 22(13), 1638–1652. doi: 10.1080/13683500.2017.1420043.
8. Andriotis, K. (2001). Strategies on resort areas and their lifecycle stages. *Tourism Review*, 56(1/2), 40–43. doi: 10.1108/eb058355.
9. Barbu, C. A., & Popa, A. (2022). Managing Tourism Seasonality in European Countries. *University Annals: Economic Sciences Series*, 22(2), 12–22. doi: 10.61801/OUAESS.2022.2.02.
10. Bojanic, D. (2005). Tourist area life cycle stage and the impact of a crisis. *ASEAN Journal on Hospitality and Tourism*, 4(2), 139–150. doi: 10.5614/ajht.2005.4.2.04.
11. Butler, R. (1998). Seasonality in tourism: Issues and implications. *The Tourist Review*, 53(3), 18–24. doi: 10.1108/eb058278.
12. Butler, R. (2005). The Tourism Area Life Cycle. Applications and Modifications. *Clevedon: Channel View Publications*, 1. doi: 10.21832/9781845410278.
13. Cannas, R. (2012). An Overview of Tourism Seasonality: Key Concepts and Policies. *Almatourism – Journal of Tourism, Culture and Territorial Development*, 3(5), 40–58. doi: 10.6092/issn.2036-5195/3120.
14. Lee, C., Bergin-Seers, S., Galloway, G., O'Mahony, B., & McMurray, A. (2008). *Seasonality in the Tourism Industry: Impacts and Strategies*. Gold Coast: CRC for Sustainable Tourism Pty Ltd.
15. Gore, S., Borde, N., Hegde Desai, P. G., & George, B. (2022). A Structured Literature Review of the Tourism Area Life Cycle Concept. *Journal of tourism, sustainability and well-being*, 10(1), 1–20. doi: 10.34623/7462-ma58.
16. Gülenç Birsen, A., & Bilim, Y. (2019). A Comparative Life Cycle Analysis of Two Mass Tourism Destinations in Turkey. *Journal of Tourism & Gastronomy Studies*, 7(2), 1290–1313. doi: 10.21325/jotags.2019.421.
17. Kubickova, M., & Li, H. (2017). Tourism competitiveness, government and tourism area life cycle (TALC) model: The evaluation of Costa Rica, Guatemala and Honduras. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 19(2), 223–234. doi: 10.1002/jtr.2105.

18. Maralbayeva, S. M., Nikiforova, N. V., & Smykova, M. R. (2021). The Destination Life Cycle Concept in Developing a Tourist Brand. Case of Mangystau of Kazakhstan. *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, 12(6), 1472–1494. doi: 10.14505//jemt.v12.6(54).05.
19. Plokhikh, R. V., & Sakypbek, M. A. (2015). Strategic planning in the context of sustainable tourism development. *Nauchnyj rezul'tat. Tekhnologii biznesa i servisa [Scientific result. Business and service technologies]*, 1(4), 11-16. doi: 10.18413 /2408-9346-2015-1-4-11-17.
20. Polyzos, S., Tsiotas, D., & Kantlis, A. (2013). Determining the tourism developmental dynamics of the Greek regions, by using TALC theory. *Tourismos*, 8(2), 159–178.
21. Rizal, P., & Asokan, R. (2014). Seasonality of tourism: a major constraint for the growth of tourism in the regional economy of Sikkim state, India. *International Journal of Current Research*, 6(06), 7211-7218.
22. Rodrigo, M., Ajala, I., & Irhanida, A. K. (2023). Qualitative analysis of a tourism area life cycle model for interacting tourism destinations. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 4, 1–12. doi: 10.1016/j.annale.2023.100093.
23. Todorovic, B. (2019). The importance of life cycle on the future development of tourist destination. *CES Working Papers*, 11(2), 143–155.